

The Effectiveness of an Individual Approach to the Prevention of Women's Crime – A Comprehensive System of Assistance

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Abstract: *This article highlights the role of the individual approach-complex assistance system in preventing women's crime, as well as criminological measures for early prevention of women's crime, the work that needs to be done in cooperation.*

A comparative analysis of the differences between this system and other crimes in the early prevention of factors causing female crime, rehabilitation of women with problems through the provision of immediate assistance, and the prevention of female crime was conducted, and conclusions were presented based on the results obtained.

Keywords: *women's crime, individual approach, comprehensive assistance, social influence, criminological measures, social prevention, criminological prevention, causes of crime, conditions of crime.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in order to prevent crime and all types of violations in general, special attention is paid to the coordination of existing social relations and the adoption of necessary measures in the social, economic, and political spheres to eliminate the causes and conditions of crimes. In particular, the development of effective methods and means of preventing violations occurring during the transition to market relations is becoming increasingly important.

In turn, it should be noted that as a result of the rejection of any crime as a legal phenomenon in a narrow sense and its recognition as a socio-legal and psychological tool, a new approach to the perpetrator's actions has emerged, and crime prevention has become the main direction in the fight against crime. The problem of crime prevention (prevention) is a controversial issue. For example, I.V. Nikitenko emphasizes that crime prevention is a set of measures aimed at eliminating the causes and conditions of crimes.

Within the framework of large-scale reforms carried out in our country, special attention is paid to ensuring a peaceful and prosperous life of the population, as well as the formation of a culture of law-abidingness and public security in our society.

In particular, a completely new mechanism and procedure for organizing work in the field of ensuring public safety based on the principle of "serving the interests of the people" have been introduced, and targeted interaction between state bodies and public structures has been established.

In order to systematically continue the work in this direction and provide social support and create decent living conditions for families and women, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2023 No. PP-401 "On additional measures to strengthen families and increase the activity of women" was adopted.

The future of society and the state is in the hands of women who bring to life and raise children who are the future of the people. But when it comes to girls, mothers who raise children of the people should find their place in society, the use of the word "criminal" is a heavy burden, like a stone thrown into society. V.N. Kudryavtsev clearly defines crime prevention, which he identifies as a specific sphere of social regulation and management of social processes, linked to the implementation of the task of eliminating crime, which affects certain objects and the activities of certain subjects of preventive activity. The definition of crime prevention as a sphere of social regulation, in our opinion, reflects the high social significance of preventing crimes that affect social relations, including various spheres of activity.

It is precisely this approach that allows us to distinguish between two main areas of preventive activity: general social prevention, characterized by its influence on various social relations that are not directly related to crime, and special criminological prevention, characterized by its influence on factors determining crime.

Crime prevention is a system that includes:

- ✓ Objects of prevention;
- ✓ Subjects of prevention;
- ✓ Measures to prevent crime.

Given that the object of crime prevention for women is the factors that cause it, in our opinion, it is advisable to consider them based on the classification of determinants.

This includes the following factors:

- ✓ socio-economic,
- ✓ cultural,
- ✓ moral,
- ✓ political,
- ✓ organizational,
- ✓ management and legal factors.

The prevention of crimes committed by women cannot be carried out separately from other crimes that are part of the criminal system. The necessary conditions for preventing female crime should be implemented alongside the elimination of existing problems in society.

It should be noted that after Uzbekistan gained state independence, its state policy in the social, economic, and political spheres underwent fundamental changes in content and essence. The main factor in state policy was aimed at fully ensuring human rights and freedoms. In this regard, the reforms implemented in the judicial system, especially the liberalization of criminal penalties, and the essence of the state's criminal law policy, are primarily aimed at ensuring personal freedoms. It was precisely because of this policy that some categories of criminals, including the definition of measures of influence in the spirit of complete humanism has been introduced in the appointment of punishment for women. Most importantly, the transition to a civil society based on market relations is defined as one of the main goals of building a new society, primarily ensuring women's rights and increasing their social role. Based on this, all preventive measures to prevent female crime should be reviewed and scientifically and theoretically substantiated based on new requirements in the legislation.

It can be said that the prevention of female crime has its own ideological and spiritual significance. Ensuring the social protection of women ensures the spiritual and material well-being of the family and the upbringing of a new generation.

To prevent women from committing crimes, it is necessary to identify factors that negatively impact their formation. Such factors arise mainly in domestic life and production.

It is true that in order to ensure the fulfillment of a specific task in society, it is necessary to create the necessary environment for it. Therefore, to prevent women from committing crimes, it is important to solve problems encountered in the spheres of production, recreation, and family life. Without solving them, it is impossible to achieve positive results in preventing female crime.

As is known, a problem that deserves special attention in everyday life is the comprehensive provision of the family. It is the strengthening of the family that is the first step in preventing many crimes committed by women. In addition to financial and material assistance provided to the family, a number of other amenities should also be created. In particular, it is necessary to allocate time for the upbringing of a child, provide medical, household, cultural and other assistance in necessary cases, as well as provide social benefits to single mothers. In our country, there are many families with many children (three or more). Based on the current laws of market relations, it is necessary to ensure that such families have sufficient income. This creates the necessary conditions for improving the material well-being of the family, especially for raising a child.

When it comes to the family, we should not overlook the need to pay special attention to the upbringing of a girl in the family. It is necessary to raise girls from an early age with elegance and elegance, to achieve the formation of feminine qualities. The acquisition of masculine qualities by a girl leads to the formation of qualities such as ruthlessness and cruelty. It is especially dangerous for girls to be unattended, out of the family, to become casually street children, or to join their ranks.

This situation leads to an escalation of criminogenic situations. In such cases, it is advisable to conduct individual preventive measures, psychological and medical assistance in necessary cases based on an individual approach with a separate register of young women.

Along with the upbringing of minors and the creation of necessary conditions for them, the establishment of strict control over their activities (by internal affairs bodies, local authorities, educational and medical personnel, as well as public activists) is of great importance.

Control work should be aimed at specific goals and have restrictive or prohibitory characteristics, as well as ensure that young women do not deviate from social skills, protect them from harmful communication, and prevent wasting time.

When eliminating female crime, it is necessary not only to solve their social and economic problems, but also to conduct certain educational work among men (especially married). Increasing the material well-being of men and the population as a whole, in turn, will help prevent some negative disorders in women's lifestyles. That is, as mentioned above, it reduces the involvement of women in a physically difficult and long-term work process. The solution to the problem lies in the re-equipment of working conditions in production using modern technical means, the creation of favorable working conditions, and most importantly, the organization of labor (ergonomics) taking into account the physiological characteristics of women. Overall, the development and implementation of a social program aimed at facilitating women's work will contribute to solving important problems.

If we look at the experience of Fergana in this regard, from August 25, 2023, to the present, the composition of regional and district-city working groups was approved to "transform the Fergana region from women's crime into a region," and the activities of the staff for working with women, which should be paid special attention, were established.

In particular, the statistical analysis of crimes committed by women, the causes and circumstances, their age, social status, family environment, inclination to committing crimes, migration or return from penitentiary institutions, etc. were thoroughly studied.

As a result of the experience of the region, women are divided into 3 categories (women in need of social protection, those who are employed, women with special needs) and a system for working with women with special needs is being developed.

- The "Mahalla Seven," that is, the chairman of the mahalla, the assistant khokim, the women's activist, the youth leader and the prevention inspector, and other responsible persons formed lists of women in each mahalla who are likely to commit crimes and become victims of crimes, filled out questionnaires to study their problems and covered them.

At the same time, the main attention was paid to addressing the causes and problems of women committing crimes, which should be paid special attention to, who are registered in the EIO, as well as the processes of conversation were organized between about 7 thousand women who should pay special attention to the questionnaire provided by the working group in the form of a sample, and this survey was conducted.

- A mechanism for creating "Fergana experience" has been developed to drastically reduce crime among women. The working group shall include heads of internal affairs bodies, the Family and Women's Department, the Civil Court of the region, the Prosecutor's Office, the Tax, Justice, the Health Department, the Preschool and School Education Departments, the Mahalla Association, the Agency for Youth Affairs, the Pension Fund, the Center for Vocational Training, the Poverty Reduction and Employment Department, the National Agency for Social Protection of the region, the Central Bank and the district administration of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Another important experience is that the questionnaire data on women, which should be paid special attention, was developed at the initiative of the Department of Internal Affairs of the Fergana region and entered into the "E-ayol" social platform, which ensures the rapid exchange of information with the responsible agencies in solving the problems of 14 categories of women: the department responsible for solving the problem was determined and sent to the responsible agencies in electronic form.

- responsible persons, who have received information on the problems of women in a short time, will take measures to solve the problems according to their relevance, and the work done to solve the problem will be included in the platform.
- the resolution of the problems included in the platform will be discussed at the end of each month by the regional commission on crime reduction among women, approved by the program.

Over the past period, in cooperation with the "Mahalla Seven" and other responsible agencies in the regions, a number of women have been prevented from entering the streets of crime on the basis of a civil work system.

The working group will be created at the level of districts and mahallas, and this year, according to the new system, it will work in accordance with the principle of individual approach - comprehensive assistance in the composition of female activists, social workers, patronage nurses and senior prevention inspectors and senior women's inspectors. The main task of the working group will be legal promotion and explanation among women who need special attention, as well as 30-40-year-old women with a relatively high proportion according to the analysis of the age of crime, and women in difficult situations, divorced, subjected to violence, and in need of social protection are taken under special supervision by social workers and medical personnel.

The main task is to include women, who should be given special attention during the activities of the headquarters established above. Each category of women was interviewed on the basis of a sample questionnaire, questionnaires were sent to organizations according to their relevance, and measures were taken to solve their problems.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 31, 2022, No. 145 and the tasks of the Republican Commission for Systematic Solving Women's Problems and Their Social Support, the fifth stage of the "Women's Notebook" was implemented in the Fergana region in 2024. An inventory was conducted among more than 800,000 women aged 30 and over in all districts and cities based on questionnaires. According to the results of the inventory, 109,506 women in 6 categories were included in the "Women's Notebook" based on the decisions of the relevant sessions of the district and city Kengashes. In March-December 2024, 109,506 women included in the "Women's Notebook" were provided with appropriate practical assistance jointly with district, city sector managers and relevant organizations.

In addition, we believe that the in-depth analysis of crimes committed by women, the development and implementation of the "Women-Family-Influent Propaganda" concept in cooperation with responsible agencies will also have an impact on achieving effectiveness. Another unique experience is the analysis of crimes committed by women in the context of the mahalla, paying special attention to mahallas where crimes are committed more often, studying the causes and conditions for the commission of crimes through the implementation of basic preventive measures, and determining measures. The makhallas were also divided into categories depending on the severity of the crime, and work was organized under the supervision of officials at the level of the head.

In the above-mentioned makhallas, work on crime prevention was organized on the basis of 6 types of prevention.

1. General preventive measures
2. Individual preventive measures
3. Special preventive measures
4. Victimological preventive measures
5. Seasonal preventive measures
6. Digital preventive measures

Due to the fact that, according to the analysis of the age of female crime, the largest share falls on women aged 31-40, the "Women's Psychological Appearance" questionnaire was formed among women of this age, and special attention was paid to working with women of this age. As an experiment, work was carried out to determine the probability of committing a crime and being a victim, to determine the psychological state of at least 50 percent of 3-4-year students studying in the direction of psychology in higher educational institutions of the region, to organize educational practice in mahallas of the red category, as well as to establish psychological conversations with women of this age. According to the analysis, the state of domestic violence also leads to the formation of aggressive behavior among women. Based on the analysis of this situation, the use of the power of representatives of religious institutions and the movement of intelligent women has been established in order to identify and suppress cases of domestic violence.

In cooperation with the "Human" social centers, social rehabilitation of women in need of social protection and victims of violence has been strengthened.

Educational work was organized with the perpetrators of violence according to the 1+7 system.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, we conclude that using a system of individual approaches to preventing women's crime will prevent it by identifying and jointly resolving several problems in one woman and timely eliminating the causes and conditions that can lead to women's crime.

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